

**STAFF WORKLOAD AND REWARD AS CORRELATES OF EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT
UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS' LEARNING OUTCOME IN UNIVERSITIES IN NORTH-
CENTRAL AND NORTH-EAST, NIGERIA**

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14729718>

ABSTRACT

This study investigated staff workload and reward systems as correlate of educational management undergraduate students' learning outcome in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria. The study adopted correlational research design, with three research questions and 2 hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population of the study was 1,388 staff and students in undergraduate Educational Management/Administration and Planning programme in the study area. The sample of the study was 341 respondents (i.e., 105 academic staff and 236 students), which was selected using multistage sampling technique. A self-constructed questionnaires titled: "Staff Workload and Reward Systems Questionnaire (SWRSQ)" plus pro-forma titled: Educational Management Final Year Students' CGPA were used as the instruments for data collection. The instruments were validated and pilot tested with Cronbach Alpha statistic showing a reliability co-efficient of 0.84 for HRMPQ. The data collected were analysed using Mean and Standard Deviation to answer the research questions; while Simple Linear and Multiple Regression Analyses were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the hypotheses revealed that there is a significant correlation between staff workload, staff reward and students' academic achievement. Collectively, the findings showed that there is a significant correlation between staff workload, staff reward and students' learning outcome. Hence, the study concluded that staff workload and staff reward are significant correlates of students' learning outcome in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria. The study recommended among others that universities' administrators should monitor and manage staff workload to prevent burnout by providing additional support or resources where necessary that can lead to improved student academic achievement.

Keywords: Staff Workload, Staff Reward Systems, Student Learning Outcome, Student Academic Achievement, Educational Management

INTRODUCTION

Education is generally referred to as any positive change of behaviour, attitude, experience that has effect on mind, character or physical appearance of the individual and it is a continuous process which goes on throughout one's life. Education is a process of transmitting knowledge and skills to younger generation through schools, colleges, universities and other mass media like radio, film, television, magazines and newspapers (Usman, 2015). In Nigeria, the Federal Government through its policy on education divide the educational systems into Basic Education (pre-primary, primary and junior

secondary school), Post Basic Education and Tertiary Education (Federal Republic of Nigeria, FRN, 2013). Tertiary education, is the level of education that provides students with instruction in school administration and planning, as well as educational management. Hence, educational management students must be well equipped in terms of their learning outcomes to attain these goals.

Learning outcomes according to Korde (2021) refers to what learners should be able to do/perform as a result of some learning experience achieved in a given course of study. It is also the statement of the knowledge, attitude and abilities individual students should possess and can demonstrate upon the completion of a learning experience. Teaching students to read, write and calculate is often considered the primary purpose of formal education, but students' regular attendance and attention in school also help to guarantee students' learning outcome (Aneth, 2017). The environment, content and processes that learners encounter in school lead to diverse results, some intended and others unintended. Quality learner outcomes are intentional, expected effects of the educational system. It includes what students know and can do, as well as the attitudes and expectations they have for themselves and their societies (Bakari & Bambi, 2021). Hence, the quality of learning outcomes includes the ability of students to demonstrate sound knowledge, values and skills in cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains of learning, which are shown by the marks/grades obtained in examinations and their attitude upon graduation. In the context of this study, students' learning outcome was limited to students' level of academic achievement in educational management courses at universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria.

In most universities, Bakari and Bambi (2021) argued that many factors constitute to the non-attainment of high students' learning outcome, as most institutions' resources are ill-equipped while some management personnel do not manage effectively the few available resources for improving students' learning outcome. Other factors that constitute low students' learning outcome, according to Aneth (2017) include funding, students' readiness to learn, teacher quality, teacher motivation, available facilities, academic content and the overall learning environment. In addition, Aithal and Suresh (2016) suggested quality of teaching, students support services, students' mental health and well-being, curricula and skills gap. Majority of these factors could be classified as resources. Resources used in the educational setting for the purpose of achieving educational goals are called educational resource and majorly include material, financial and human resources. The chief among these resources is the human resource. A university's human resource include the academic and non-academic staffs that have been employed by the institution to help in the teaching and learning process. These staff take decisions, which provide the knowledge, energy and the co-operation through which the university objectives, which include quality students' learning outcome could be achieved. Hence, staff effective management through staff workload management and reward systems are essential to the realisation of quality students' learning outcome.

Staff workload is an all-encompassing and wide-ranging activity that consumes employees' time. This includes but is not limited to executing professional duties and responsibilities, as well as the direct and indirect pursuit of work-related interests (Pace, D'Urso, Zappulla & Pace, 2019). Rahman and Avan (2016) defined academic staff workload as the amount of time lecturers spent in performing a portfolio of research and teaching tasks, facilitating co-curricular activities and being involved in meetings. In Nigeria, the term workload refers to teaching subjects, administrative duties, students' supervision and other activities like research, students support and community service. Nonetheless, overworked staffs are less likely to carry the visions, energy and adaptability, hopeful and compassionate engagement essential for effective classroom instruction (Grenata, 2014). Thus, school managers should consider workload factors when providing support and using reward systems to encourage staff effectiveness on the job.

Staff rewards according to Chukwuma, Agbanu, Agbo and Ezenwa (2022) refer to programmes by different organizations to reward performance and motivate employees on individual and group level. In the university, it is the recognition and incentives provided to staff members in acknowledgment of their contributions, achievements and performance within the university. Rewards are therefore designed to motivate and retain talented staff, enhance job satisfaction and foster a positive work environment and could be directly and indirectly involved in the vision and mission of the organization. In any organization, rewarded staff tend to be efficient, hardworking and give maximum output to ensure organizational goals are achieved. Reward systems therefore have the potential to improve teaching excellence in a university. This could be possible when a university recognizes and rewards outstanding teaching performance, staff members may be motivated to continually enhance pedagogical approaches, innovate teaching methods and strive for excellence in the classroom (Chumari, Were & Rintari, 2018).

From the foregoing, it could be conceived that staff working condition and appraisal in education plays a critical role in educational institutions by shaping the work environment, supporting staff development and ensuring the effective delivery of education. In the context of undergraduate educational management programmes in the study area, staff working condition and appraisal have the potential to significantly impact students' learning outcome either positively or negatively. Thus, there was a need to investigate and understand the specific correlation between human resource management and the learning outcomes of undergraduate educational management students especially in universities in the study area. Hence, it was in view of the aforementioned discussions that the researchers investigated the correlation between staff working condition, appraisal and students' learning outcome in educational management programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The current situation in educational management programmes across universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria reveals a troubling trend of poor students' learning outcome, characterized by low academic achievement. Despite efforts to enhance educational quality, the researchers observed that some students in educational management programmes in the study area continue to exhibit disengagement, lack of motivation, and underperformance in their academic pursuits. This persistent issue not only undermines the effectiveness of the educational management curriculum but also jeopardizes the future competence of graduates who are expected to lead and innovate in the educational sector.

The consequences of these poor learning outcomes are far-reaching. Graduates with low academic achievement and poor attitudes are less likely to excel in professional settings, diminishing ability to contribute effectively to the educational system. Moreover, the reputation of the institutions offering educational management programme suffers, potentially leading to a decrease in student enrolment and a lack of trust from stakeholders. The broader educational landscape is also affected, as poorly trained educational managers may propagate ineffective practices, further entrenching systemic issues within the sector. Addressing these challenges is critical to ensuring that the next generation of educational leaders is equipped with the skills, knowledge, and mindset needed to drive positive change.

In essence, the success or failure of educational management programmes in the study area hinges on the strategic implementation of HRM practices such as staff workload and reward system that prioritize the well-being and professional growth of academic staff. However, there are no empirical evidence in the study area to support the relationship between HRM practices (staff workload and reward system) and students' learning outcome.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The study sought to determine the correlation between staff workload, staff reward system and educational management undergraduate students' learning outcome in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria. The specific objectives of this study were to determine whether:

1. Staff workload is a correlate of educational management undergraduate students' learning outcome in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria.
2. Staff reward system is a correlate of educational management undergraduate students' learning outcome in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

In order to achieve the specific objectives of the study, the following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the level of staff workload in educational management undergraduate programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria?
2. What is the level of staff reward system in educational management undergraduate programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria?
3. What is the mean score of educational management undergraduate students' cumulative grade points average in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- H₀₁:** There is no significant correlation between staff workload and educational management undergraduate students' learning outcome in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria.
- H₀₂:** There is no significant correlation between staff reward system and educational management undergraduate students' learning outcome in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical framework of this study was based on the Social Exchange Theory as postulated by George Homans in 1958 and Social Cognitive Theory propounded by psychologist Albert Bandura in 1986. According to Social Exchange Theory (SET), individuals engage in social interactions based on the calculation of costs and benefits. They seek to maximize rewards and minimize costs in their relationships. SET highlights the importance of recognition and appreciation in the exchange relationship. Recognizing and appreciating the efforts and achievements of lecturers through awards, accolades and public acknowledgment can positively reinforce their contributions. Such recognition can enhance lecturers' job satisfaction and commitment to the university.

The SCT, is a psychological framework that emphasizes the reciprocal interaction between personal factors, environmental influences and behaviour. SCT stated that individuals learn and develop through a process of observation, imitation and the cognitive processing of information. The relatedness of Social Cognitive Theory, as developed by Albert Bandura to the current study is because it provides insights students' learning outcome through observational learning, self-efficacy, modelling teacher behaviour, self-regulation, feedback and reinforcement. SCT highlights the importance of

observational learning in educational settings. Students can learn from observing others, such as teachers, peers, or even multimedia sources. In addition, lecturers serve as important models for students and their behaviour can impact students' learning outcome.

Staffing Workload and Students' Learning Outcome

According to Amie-Ogan and Fekarurhobo (2021), workload refers to the duties that an employee is expected to perform as part of his job description. It also refers to the collection of legal obligations placed on an employee (a member of the academic staff), which must be fulfilled at a specific time. Amie-Ogan and Fekarurhobo further examined perceived influence of work overload on academic staff job performance in universities in Rivers State. The result of the analysed data revealed among others that teaching of many courses in a semester, supervision of large number of undergraduate projects and post-graduate theses influence job performance of academic staff in universities in Rivers State to a high extent, thus affecting student outcome. Also, Amini-Philips and Okonmah (2020) investigated lecturers' workload and productivity in Universities in Delta State, Nigeria. It was found that, there is significant high negative relationship between lecturers teaching workload, marking workload, supervision of students' project workload, research workload and participation in community service workload and productivity in Universities in Delta State independently and jointly taken. These thereby impact lecturers' contribution to student outcome; however, its true impact was unknown in the study area.

Staff Reward Systems and Students' Learning Outcome

Reward is a management control tool that makes sure every employee in the company performs their tasks in line with what the company wants (Onuorah, Okeke & Ikehukwu, 2019). Idigo (2023) investigated the incentives and performance of workers in tertiary institutions in Anambra and Enugu state, Nigeria. It was discovered that monetary incentives have a positive significant influence workers' productivity in Nigerian organization; Nonmonetary incentives have a positive significant influence workers' productivity in Nigerian organization; while career development has negative significant effect on workers' productivity in Nigerian organization. Also, Okoli, Okoli and Nuel-Okoli (2020) examined the relationship that exists between reward management practices and employee performance in selected public universities in the South-East Nigeria. The findings revealed that there was a significant positive relationship existing between distributive justice and employee commitment (cal. $r .893 > \text{crit. } r 0.098$) and there was a significant positive relationship existing between employee recognition and job satisfaction (cal. $r .942 > \text{crit. } r 0.098$). In addition, Bossey (2022) examined the effect of reward on organizational performance in universities in Edo State, Nigeria. The study aimed to determine the effect of salary increase, cash bonus, recognition, promotion and career development on organizational performance. The study found that salary increase, cash bonus, promotion, recognition and career development have significant effect on organizational performance and student outcome respectively. Although this is unknown in the study area, which called for the need of this study.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the correlational research design. This study was carried out in North-Central and North-East Geopolitical Zones of Nigeria. The North Central Zone includes Benue, Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Niger, Plateau States, and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), where Nigeria's capital city, Abuja, is situated. On the other hand, the North-East Zone comprises of Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba, and Yobe states. The population of the study was 1,388 respondents (210 academic staff and 1,178 final-year students) in undergraduate Educational Management/Administration and Planning degree programme at public universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria. The sample size of this study was 341 respondents (105 academic staff and 236 final year students) in undergraduate Educational Management/Administration and

Planning degree programme of public universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria which represented 50% of the population of academic staff and 20% of the entire population of final year students (Gall, Gall & Borg, 2007). Therefore, the researchers used the multistage sampling technique (that comprised of cluster sampling, simple random, purposive, proportionate and convenience sampling techniques).

The instruments that were used for data collection in this study were a self-structured questionnaire and pro-forma. The self-structured questionnaire was titled: “Staff Workload and Reward Systems Questionnaire (SWRSQ)” while the pro-forma was titled: “Educational Management Final Year Students’ CGPA”. The research instruments were validated by four experts, three from the Department of Physical Sciences Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola, while the fourth was from the Department of Educational Foundation, Taraba State University, Jalingo. The SWRSQ was subjected to reliability testing through the Cronbach Alpha coefficient, which revealed an internal consistency of 0.84, that meant the instrument was reliable. The data were gathered through a letter of introduction and the aid of four research assistants. At the end of the data collection exercise, 324 (103 from staff and 221 from students) valid questionnaires were retrieved which amounts to 95% of the total questionnaires administered. Hence, mean, standard deviation and simple linear regression were used to analysed the data collected.

RESULTS

The results are presented in the order of research questions and hypotheses from Table 1 – 5. For the research questions, the keys represent: n = no of respondents, Std. Dev = Standard Deviation, HL = High Level, ML = Moderate Level and LL = Low Level.

Research Questions

Research Question 1: What is the level of staff workload in educational management undergraduate programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Level of Staff Workload in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria

S/N	ITEMS	n = 103	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1.	Lecturing large classes could impact lecturers’ health		4.36	1.08	HL
2.	Having to teach many courses often makes it difficult for lecturers to adequately produce students’ results on time		3.92	1.27	HL
3.	Conducting test/examination for large number of students often impact lecturers’ ability to deliver properly		3.89	1.15	HL
4.	Most lecturers have little time for research work		3.95	1.37	HL
5.	Lecturers often supervise students on community services amidst teaching functions		4.21	1.27	HL
6.	Serving as examination officers amidst research/publication activities impacts lecturers’ effectiveness		4.11	1.22	HL
7.	Invigilating students’ examinations under tension due to poor accommodation.		4.08	1.09	HL
	Grand Mean		4.07		HL

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

From the above Table 1 shows that staff workload in educational management undergraduate programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria has a grand mean score of 4.07, which indicate a high level.

Research Question 2: What is the level of staff reward system in educational management undergraduate programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Level of Staff Reward System in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria

S/N	ITEMS	n = 103	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
8.	University staff are often given gifts during festivity to motivate them		3.67	1.57	HL
9.	The Head of Department frequently commend faculty staff personnel on a job well done		3.64	1.41	HL
10.	The university staff are rewarded for providing effective academic mentoring to students		3.27	1.46	ML
11.	The university holds an annual ceremony to honour its top staff		3.33	1.37	ML
12.	The university’s health insurance benefits are enough to cover all lecturers’ medical expenses		3.96	1.23	HL
13.	The university administrators incentivize staff to engage in innovative research		3.62	1.39	HL
14.	The allowance offered at the university for specified duties (such as Teaching Practice supervision) is sufficient to cover the expenses incurred		3.81	1.41	HL
Grand Mean			3.61		HL

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

From the above Table 2 shows that staff reward system in educational management undergraduate programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria has a grand mean score of 3.61, which indicate a high level.

Research Question 3: What is the mean score of educational management undergraduate students’ cumulative grade points average in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Mean Score of Educational Management Undergraduate Students’ Cumulative Grade Points Average in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria

S/N	ITEMS	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1.	Taraba State University EDM Final Year Students’ CGPA	3.29	0.62	ML
2.	University of Abuja EDM Final Year Students’ CGPA	3.13	0.48	ML
3.	Benue State University EDM Final Year Students’ CGPA	3.64	0.93	ML
4.	Federal University, Kashere EDM Final Year Students’ CGPA	3.23	0.71	ML
5.	Prince Abubakar Audu University, Kogi EDM Final Year Students’ CGPA	2.78	0.56	ML
Grand Mean		3.21		ML

Source: Exams and Records Department of the University

The above table reveals a grand mean of 3.21. This means that students’ cumulative grade points average amongst 2022/2023 final year educational management undergraduate students in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria is at a moderate level.

Hypotheses Testing

The null hypotheses were tested using Linear Regression Analysis at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the following acronym stands as; df = degree of freedom; R = correlation co-efficient and sig = level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant correlation between staff workload and educational management undergraduate students’ learning outcome in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria.

Table 4a: Model Summary of the Correlation between Staff Workload and Students’ Academic Achievement in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.248 ^a	0.061	0.052	1.101

a. Predictors: (Constant), Staff Workload

Table 4a is a model summary that presents the results of the regression analysis examining the correlation between the predictor variable (staff workload) and the dependent variable (students’ academic achievement). The coefficient of determination (R-squared) is a measure of how well the independent variable (staff workload) explain the variance in the dependent variable (students’ academic achievement). The results reveal that 5.2% of the variation in academic achievement could be attributed to staff workload. The results also show that staff workload has a weak positive correlation with academic achievement as indicated by the r – value of 0.248.

Table 4b: Summary of ANOVA of Linear Regression of Staff Workload and Students’ Academic Achievement in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	8.000	1	8.000	6.595	0.012 ^b
	Residual	122.524	101	1.213		
	Total	130.524	102			

a. Dependent Variable: Students’ Academic Achievement

b. Predictors: (Constant), Staff Workload

The Table 4b presents the results of a statistical analysis (ANOVA) conducted to investigate the correlation between staff workload and students’ academic achievement in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria. The result reveals that there is a significant correlation between staff workload and students’ academic achievement in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria, $F(1, 101) = 6.595, p < 0.05$. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected, since the p–value is less than 0.05 level of significance.

Table 4c: Coefficients of the Correlation between Staff Workload and Students’ Academic Achievement in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.963	0.444		4.424	0.000
	Staff Workload	0.271	0.106	0.248	2.568	0.012

a. Dependent Variable: Students’ Academic Achievement

The outcome in Table 4c reveals the Beta coefficient derived from the regression analysis assessing the correlation between staff workload and students’ academic achievement. The constant value (B = 1.963) indicates the starting point or intercept of the model. The coefficient for staff workload (B = 0.271) signifies that for every one-unit increase in the staff workload variable, the dependent variable (students’ academic achievement) is expected to increase by 0.271 units, assuming all other factors remain constant. This positive coefficient suggests that better staff workload is associated with improved students’ academic achievement, reflecting a direct and proportional relationship between the two variables.

Ho2: There is no significant correlation between staff reward system and educational management undergraduate students’ learning outcome in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria.

Table 5a: Model Summary of the Correlation between Staff Reward System and students’ Academic Achievement in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.646 ^a	0.417	0.412	0.868

a. Predictors: (Constant), Staff Reward System

Table 5a shows a model summary that demonstrates how the independent variable accounts for the variance in the dependent variable and the strength of correlation between the variables. The results reveal that 41.2% of the variation in students’ academic achievement could be attributed to staff reward system. The results also show that there is moderate correlation between staff reward system and students’ academic achievement as indicated by the r – value of 0.646.

Table 5b: Summary of ANOVA of Linear Regression of the Correlation between Staff Reward System and Students’ Academic Achievement in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	54.483	1	54.483	72.366	0.000 ^b
	Residual	76.041	101	0.753		
	Total	130.524	102			

a. Dependent Variable: Students’ Academic Achievement

b. Predictors: (Constant), Staff Reward System

The results of analysis in Table 5b presents analysis of variance (ANOVA) of linear regression analysis that aims to examine the correlation between staff reward system on students’ academic achievement in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria. The result reveals that there is a significant correlation between staff reward system and students’ academic achievement in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria, $F(1, 101) = 72.366, p < 0.05$. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected since the p – value is less than 0.05 level of significance.

Table 5c: Coefficients of Correlation between Staff Reward System and Students’ Academic Achievement in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
		Coefficients		Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.850	0.274		3.098	0.003
	Staff Reward System	0.614	0.072	0.646	8.507	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Students’ Academic Achievement

The outcome in Table 5c reveals the Beta coefficient derived from the regression analysis assessing the correlation between staff reward system and students’ academic achievement. The constant value (B = 0.85) indicates the starting point

or intercept of the model. The coefficient for staff reward ($B = 0.614$) signifies that for every one-unit increase in the staff reward variable, the dependent variable (students' academic achievement) is expected to increase by 0.614 units, assuming all other factors remain constant. This positive coefficient suggests that better staff reward is associated with improved students' academic achievement, reflecting a direct and proportional relationship between the two variables.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study also found in Table 1 that staff workload in educational management undergraduate programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria is at a high level, with a grand mean of 4.07. This finding however concurred with Avirmed and Mishigdorj (2023); Amie-Ogan and Fekarurhobo (2021); Amini-Philips and Okonmah's (2020) findings that most lecturers are often involved in high workload in tertiary institutions, that often include teaching, supervision, inspection and participation in different committees in the institution. Although, the finding disagrees with that of Hosain (2016); Ogundare, Ambode and Babalola (2022) studies that revealed a moderate staff workload in the school system. However, the implication of the study finding is that the high level of staff workload signals a significant concern within the educational management undergraduate program. A heavy workload can lead to stress, burnout, and decreased job satisfaction among faculty members. It may also affect the quality of teaching, research output, and overall productivity.

Hypothesis 1 was rejected, as the result showed that there is a significant correlation between staff workload and students' academic achievement in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria, $F(1, 101) = 6.595$, $p < 0.05$. The finding is in disagreement with Igbokwe, Itoya and Eziuzo's (2020) finding that long hours of work as a source of job stress have negative and significant effect on employee and students' performance in tertiary institutions. In addition, Hosain (2016) revealed that heavy workload is negatively correlated to students' academic performance. The implication of this finding is that it implies that high staff workload levels may have a negative impact on students' academic performance. A heavy workload can potentially lead to faculty members having limited time and resources to dedicate to teaching, providing feedback, and supporting student learning. As a result, students may experience challenges in mastering course content, completing assignments, and achieving their academic goals.

The study also found in Table 2 that staff reward system in educational management undergraduate programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria is at a high level, with a grand mean of 3.61. The finding agreed with the findings of Ali and Ahmed (2018); Chumari, Were and Rintari (2018); Bossey (2022) that there is high level of staff rewards in tertiary institutions, which often include, recognition, health benefits, earned allowances etc. This finding however disagreed with Okoli, Okoli and Nuel-Okoli (2020); Alkandi, Khan, Fallatah, Alabdulhadi, Alanizan and Alharbi (2023) studies which revealed that staff reward systems are usually moderately carried out. The study finding however suggests a robust reward system is crucial for motivating faculty members, acknowledging their efforts, and retaining talent within the institution. It can include various forms of recognition such as salary increases, bonuses, awards, professional development opportunities, and non-monetary rewards like public acknowledgment and career advancement opportunities.

In addition, hypothesis 2 was rejected, as the result showed that there is a correlation between staff reward system and students' academic achievement in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria, $F(1, 101) = 72.366$, $p < 0.05$. The finding concurred with Ayeni, Fred, Uwague, Olojede, Fayemi, Ajagbe and Osazuwa (2022) results that there is a linear relationship between the reward system and staff' commitment to students' performance. Also, Bossey (2022) study revealed that reward has a significant positive effect on organizational performance, in the sampled universities in Edo State. However, the finding is in disagreement with the finding of Ghasi and

Onyejiaku (2018) that the level of staff satisfaction with the reward system implemented by the tertiary institutions is low (computed z-value of 24.385 against 1.645 and significance of 0.000) ($z = 24.385 > \text{at } p < 0.05$) during the period studied. Thus, the hypothesis finding suggests that a well-functioning reward system can also impact students' academic performance. When faculty members are motivated and rewarded for their contributions, they are more likely to be effective teachers, mentors, and advisors, which can positively influence students' learning outcome.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the study concludes that staff workload and staff reward system significantly correlate with students' learning outcome in Universities of North-Central and North-East, Nigeria. The results revealed that effective HRM practices are associated with more positive students' learning outcome. Manageable workloads and meaningful reward systems collectively contribute to creating a supportive and engaging learning environment. This, in turn, fosters positive student attitudes towards the university and enhances academic achievement among students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made;

1. University administrators should monitor and manage staff workload to prevent burnout by providing additional support or resources where necessary that can lead to improved student academic achievement.
2. The University management should create a reward system that incentivizes innovative teaching methods and academic excellence. This approach can have a direct impact on improving student academic outcomes.
3. The University Human Resource Management and Academic Affairs Committee should adopt a comprehensive human resource management approach that prioritizes staff support, which will ultimately lead to better academic outcomes for students.

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